

Damage Propagation in CFRP Laminates due to Lateral Load

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SUMMARY: This paper describes a mechanism of damage accumulation in cross-ply CFRP laminates $[0_2/90_2]_{2S}$ subjected to out-of-plane loading. Drop-weight impact and static indentation tests were carried out, and induced delaminations and transverse cracks were observed by ultrasonic C-scan and microscope. Both tests gave essentially the same results for damage modes, delamination size and deformations of the laminates. Initial damage was a crack in the bottom 0° layer caused by bending and an elongated delamination along the bending crack tip. After that, transverse cracks in the middle 90° layer occurred with decreasing the contact force between the specimen and the indenter. Measured local strains near impact point changed in-plane tensile condition during impact. Numerical models with cohesive interface elements were used to simulate the propagation of multiple delaminations and transverse cracks under static indentation. Two types of analysis models, delamination-transverse crack model and only delamination model, are considered in order to examine the effect of transverse crack on the delamination propagation. The result obtained from the delaminations-transverse cracks model well explains the characteristics of the realistic damage. The effect of transverse cracks on predicted delamination propagation is significant.

KEYWORDS: Delamination, Transverse crack, Low velocity impact, Indentation, Finite Element Analysis, Cohesive element, Progressive Failure Analysis

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the use of composite structures has increased to achieve a weight reduction with a high strength and stiffness. However, the structures made of composite laminates are susceptible to low-velocity impact damage because they have no reinforcement through the thickness and material discontinuities in their interfaces [1-2]. Delamination is one of the main failure factors in laminated structures, being difficult to be detected from outside. This damage can cause a severe reduction of compressive performance of the structure, which is well known as CAI (Compression After Impact) problem [3-4]. Design loads of the structures are often limited by the degraded compressive strength. Therefore, it is important to understand how the low-velocity impact damages composite laminates to utilize their advantages.

The low-velocity impact test is often simulated by the static indentation test, neglecting the dynamic effects on the structure response. The damage configuration due to the

static indentation is similar to that of the low-velocity impact [5]. It is reasonable to investigate the low-velocity impact damage under static loading. The impact damage in composite laminates consists of a delamination, a transverse crack and a fiber failure. The accumulation process of these damages is quite complex, hence the convenient analysis tools, which can simulate the different damage modes, are required. With the increase of computer performance, the finite element analysis can be a powerful tool to simulate the behavior of impacted laminates. Some researchers have proposed a cohesive crack model based on Dugdale-Barenblatt cohesive zone approach [6-7], which is only applicable when the cohesive zone size is small compared with the size of crack and specimen. In this model, crack growth is governed by the traction and displacement relation on the crack surface in the vicinity of a crack tip. The cohesive zone model is convenient and attractive to simulate the delamination propagation in composite laminates since the fracture interface can be prescribed. Various cohesive models are developed and proposed to simulate the crack-like damages in composite materials [8-12].

In this paper, a damage growth problem in cross-ply CFRP laminates is experimentally studied and analyzed by using a three-dimensional cohesive interface element. The drop-weight impact and static indentation tests are performed for comparison of the results. The numerical model is used to simulate the growth of multiple delaminations and transverse cracks in cross-ply laminates subjected to static indentation. The coupling effect between the transverse cracks and delamination on laminates behavior and final damage shape are considered.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Specimens

The specimens used in this study were T800/3633 carbon fiber/epoxy laminates manufactured by Toray Industries, Inc. The reason for employing this material system was that abundance of basic material data are available on JAXA-ACDB web site [13]. The stacking sequence of the specimen is $[0_2/90_2]_{2S}$ with a nominal fiber volume fraction of 58% and an average thickness of 2.26 mm. A type of specimen selected here is based on the CAI test method, Half-SACMA (H-SACMA) [14]. This method is proposed as a more economical method than often used SACMA method [15] in specimen size. The specimen of 76 mm width and 102 mm length was cut out of the mother plate. In order to examine the behavior of the laminate during impact or static tests, uniaxial strain gages were glued on the top and bottom surfaces of the specimen. The dimensions of the H-SACMA specimen and the gage locations are shown in Fig. 1.

Impact and Static indentation tests

Impact was given to the center of the specimen by the Instron 9250HV drop-weight impact test machine with a 15.9 mm (5/8 inch) hemispherical steel tup. The total mass of the impactor was 5.07 kg. A variety of impact energies from 5.02 J to 15.07 J were obtained by changing the drop height, where impact velocities ranged from 1.42 m/s to 2.42 m/s. Support fixture consists of a support base with a cut-out of 80 mm x 60 mm and a picture frame type support holder with the same size cut-out. Specimens were placed on the support base and the holder was cramped to the base by fasteners. Contact force history of the specimen was obtained by the instrumented tup. Strains were measured by a high-speed data acquisition device (YOKOGAWA WE7000) with a sampling rate of 100 kHz during an impact event. Static indentation tests were carried out by the INSTRON 4400R screw driven testing machine. Specimens were tested at a constant displacement rate of 0.5 mm/min. The indenter and support fixture used in the static test were the same as those of the impact test. The energy given by the indenter was calculated from the area under the force-deflection curve of the

Fig. 1: Schematic view of H-SACMA specimens and location of strain gages

saw. The sliced specimens were mounted in epoxy resin and then ground by abrasive papers to observe an initial damage and damage growth by the optical microscope.

Test Results and Discussions

Typical C-scan images of the specimen after the impact and static indentation tests are shown in Fig. 3, where each specimen was applied to 5.02 J and 4.54 J, respectively. It was found that the characteristics of the damage shape are quite similar in both tests, while the damage size of the impact test was slightly larger than that of static test because applied energies were different. The typical relationships between a contact force and a displacement are shown in Fig. 4. In the loading process, the curves show the good agreement between both tests. The contact force increases linearly with displacement until it reaches a peak. The peak appears at the same load level in both tests and load dropped suddenly after the peak of 1.8 kN, which is associated with the energy release caused by the damage initiation. After that, the load increases nonlinearly. The unloading response shows the crucial difference between two cases because the precise deflection of the specimen after impact could not be obtained by the impact machine. The deflection after impact is calculated from standard equation of motion for an object traveling in a straight line being subjected to an opposing force. However, both tests gave essentially the same results for damage size and deformations of the laminates.

specimen. Fig. 2 shows an overview of the both test apparatus and a specimen placed inside the support fixture.

After the tests, the size and shape of delaminations and transverse cracks were inspected by the ultrasonic C-scan for all specimens. The Krautkramer SDS 5400R was used for the ultrasonic C-scan system. The specimen immersed in water was scanned in pulsed-echo mode by a 5.0 MHz transducer. In the static indentation tests, some tests were stopped at a low load level and the specimen was cut into slices by diamond fine

(a) Impact test machine

(b) Static indentation test machine

(c) Support fixture

Fig. 2: Overview of test apparatus and support fixture

Fig. 3: Typical damages due to impact and static tests

Fig. 4: Typical force-deflection curves

Next, the different stages of the damage process were observed after static tests. Three specimens were loaded up to three different energy levels, (a) 0.89 J, (b) 1.55 J and (c) 5.79 J and whose load-deflection curves are shown as Fig. 5. Each of the three curves corresponds to following load level; (a) first cracking noise was perceived by the ear at 1.4 kN, (b) the sudden load-drop occurred with a sharp noise at 1.9 kN, (c) damages propagate significantly at 3.0 kN after the load-drop. Figure 6 shows ultrasonic C-scan images of plane view of accumulated delamination and side view. The depth information from the top surface is distinguished by different colors in this figure. Figure 7 shows the micrographs of the cross-section under indented position for the each load level in Fig. 5.

From the micrographs, the first damage initiated without load-drop of the load-deflection curve, whose modes are a single bending crack in the bottom layer and transverse cracks in the second bottom layer (90° layer). These crack-like damages caused the small elongated delamination in the lowest $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interface shown as Fig. 6(a). The delamination propagates along the bending crack tip. Then, the load-drop was caused by the transverse cracks inclined at 45° in the middle 90° layer, whose tips produce and connect with the delaminations. The transverse cracks create an inverse pine tree, which is the same characterization as thin laminate behavior under impact loading [16]. After load-drop, the number of transverse cracks increases and delaminations propagates significantly in the same shape. In present study, delaminations in the lowest $90^\circ/0^\circ$ interface and the third $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interface were larger than other delaminations. The number of transverse cracks in the backside layers is larger than that in topside. Figure 8(a) shows load and typical strain histories during the impact test.

Fig. 5: Load-deflection curves for different energy levels; (a) First cracking noise was perceived (0.89 J), (b) Sudden load-drop occurred with a sharp noise (1.55 J), (c) Damages propagate significantly (5.97 J)

Strains were obtained from the back-to-back strain gages shown as Figure 1. Strain at the gage S2-1a jumps after 2 msec because the gage was broken by the bending crack propagation at that time. Load-drop appeared at 2.2 msec and strain S1-3b reduced, where the transverse cracks initiated in the middle 90° layer and the associated delamination propagated. At low load level, the bending of the laminate is dominant in the 0° direction (S1-1b, S2-1b), but the compressive strain at the gage S1-1b changes to tensile strain with

Fig. 6: Ultrasonic C-scan images for different load levels due to static indentation

load increases. The in-plane stiffness becomes dominant compared to the bending stiffness with the increase of load. Therefore, the laminate in the 0° direction becomes tensile condition even in the top surface. On the other hand, bending and in-plane stresses induce large tensile strains on the backside of the laminates, hence there are many cracks in the backside layers. At the maximum load, strains show drastic change due to delamination propagation under the strain gages. Similar behavior and same strain levels were shown in case of static indentation test as shown in Fig. 8(b).

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

Formulation of the Cohesive Interface Element

In order to consider the damage growth mechanism in cross-ply laminates, numerical analysis using a three-dimensional cohesive element was conducted. The geometry of the cohesive element is shown in Fig. 9. The $x - y - z$ and $\xi - \eta$ are global and local coordinate systems, respectively. The cohesive element used here consists of 16 nodes and thickness is zero. The cohesive element is introduced into the interface between ordinary 20-node solid elements to model delaminations and transverse cracks. These damages can propagate only along the element boundaries. The stiffness of the cohesive elements is reduced when these damages occur. The constitutive relation of the cohesive element is derived by a specific separation energy density which is a function of relative displacements. The separation of the element is divided into two modes, opening mode (Mode I) and sliding mode (Mode II and III). Before deformation, node i in the lower surface and node i' in the upper surface have the same coordinate in the model. The relative sliding displacements Δu , Δv and opening displacement Δw are defined as

(a) At first noise (0.89 J)

(b) After sudden load-drop (1.55 J)

(c) Damages propagate significantly (5.97 J)

Fig. 7: Micrographs of the cross-section for different load levels due to static indentation

Fig. 8: Load and typical strain histories during impact and static test

$$\Delta u = \sum_{i=1}^8 \phi_i(\xi, \eta) \Delta u_i, \quad \Delta v = \sum_{i=1}^8 \phi_i(\xi, \eta) \Delta v_i, \quad \Delta w = \sum_{i=1}^8 \phi_i(\xi, \eta) \Delta w_i \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta u_i = u_{i'} - u_i, \quad \Delta v_i = v_{i'} - v_i, \quad \Delta w_i = w_{i'} - w_i$$

where $\phi_i(\xi, \eta)$ is the shape function corresponding to the adjacent elements, and u_i, v_i, w_i and $u_{i'}, v_{i'}, w_{i'}$ are components of nodal displacement at nodes i and i' respectively. The separation energy density per unit area stored in the element is defined by a function of the relative displacements as follows.

$$\Phi = G_c \{1 - \exp(-\varphi)\} + f(\Delta w) \quad (2)$$

$$\varphi = \alpha \Delta w^2 + \beta (\Delta u^2 + \Delta v^2)$$

$$f(\Delta w) = \begin{cases} k_c \Delta w^2 & (\Delta w < 0) \\ 0 & (\Delta w \geq 0) \end{cases}$$

where

and where G_c is a critical total energy release rate, and α and β are coefficients which determine the critical tractions and critical relative displacements. The second term of the right-hand side $f(\Delta w)$ is the penalty function introduced to the contact problem. When the relative displacement Δw is negative, the normal penalty stiffness k_c is applied to prevent the interface from overlapping. The tractions in each direction at node i are given in the following forms.

Fig. 9: Geometry of the present cohesive element

$$\begin{aligned}
T_{ui} &= \iint_{A_e} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \Delta u} \cdot \phi_i dA_e = \iint_{A_e} 2\beta G_{sc} \Delta u \cdot \exp(-\beta(\Delta u^2 + \Delta v^2)) \cdot \phi_i dA_e \\
T_{vi} &= \iint_{A_e} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \Delta v} \cdot \phi_i dA_e = \iint_{A_e} 2\beta G_{sc} \Delta v \cdot \exp(-\beta(\Delta u^2 + \Delta v^2)) \cdot \phi_i dA_e \\
T_{wi} &= \iint_{A_e} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \Delta w} \cdot \phi_i dA_e = \iint_{A_e} \left\{ 2\alpha G_{nc} \Delta w \cdot \exp(-\alpha \Delta w^2) + f'(\Delta w) \right\} \cdot \phi_i dA_e
\end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

where $dA_e = |\mathbf{J}| d\xi d\eta$, \mathbf{J} : Jacobian ($i = 1$ to 8)

Tangent stiffness matrix \mathbf{K}_t of the element is derived by the derivative of the traction vector \mathbf{T} with respect to the nodal displacements $\Delta \mathbf{u}$ as

$$\delta \mathbf{f}_i = \mathbf{K}_{t,ij} \delta \Delta \mathbf{u}_j = \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}_i}{\partial \Delta \mathbf{u}_j} \delta \Delta \mathbf{u}_j \tag{4}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
K_{uu,ij} &= \frac{\partial T_{ui}}{\partial u_j} = 2\beta G_{sc} \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 (1 - 2\beta \Delta u^2) \cdot \exp(-\beta(\Delta u^2 + \Delta v^2)) \cdot \phi_i \cdot \phi_j \cdot |\mathbf{J}| d\xi d\eta \\
K_{vv,ij} &= \frac{\partial T_{vi}}{\partial v_j} = 2\beta G_{sc} \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 (1 - 2\beta \Delta v^2) \cdot \exp(-\beta(\Delta u^2 + \Delta v^2)) \cdot \phi_i \cdot \phi_j \cdot |\mathbf{J}| d\xi d\eta \\
K_{uv,ij} &= \frac{\partial T_{ui}}{\partial v_j} = -4\beta^2 G_{sc} \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 \Delta u \cdot \Delta v \cdot \exp(-\beta(\Delta u^2 + \Delta v^2)) \cdot \phi_i \cdot \phi_j \cdot |\mathbf{J}| d\xi d\eta \\
K_{ww,ij} &= \frac{\partial T_{wi}}{\partial w_j} = 2\alpha G_{nc} \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 \left[(1 - 2\alpha \Delta w^2) \cdot \exp(-\alpha \Delta w^2) + f''(\Delta w) \right] \cdot \phi_i \cdot \phi_j \cdot |\mathbf{J}| d\xi d\eta \\
K_{uw,ij} &= K_{wu,ij} = \frac{\partial T_{ui}}{\partial w_j} = 0, \quad K_{vw,ij} = K_{wv,ij} = \frac{\partial T_{vi}}{\partial w_j} = 0
\end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Figure 10 illustrates the energy density function and constitutive relations for opening and sliding modes. The tractions are plotted against the relative opening displacement Δw and sliding displacement Δu (Δv). The traction becomes a maximum value T_{wc} (or T_{uc} , T_{vc}) at a critical relative displacement Δw_c (or Δu_c , Δv_c), and then decrease to zero at Δw_0 (Δu_0 , Δv_0) at which energy density function reaches a critical energy release rate G_c . The shape of a traction-displacement curve and different weights to the sliding and normal opening displacements contribution are determined by the coefficients α and β . The maximum traction value can set to be the interfacial debonding strength. The element separates completely when damage parameter $D = \Phi/G_c$ reaches the value of 1.0 and then all the cohesive forces vanish. Once the element separates completely, a damage parameter is stored in stiffness calculation in order to prevent the recovery of the interface in unloading process. The component of a tangent stiffness reduces to very small value (10^{-20}) once the damage parameter is introduced. The cohesive zone near the crack tip is schematically illustrated in Fig. 10(d). Since the neighborhood of the crack tip area deforms significantly, the elements should be sufficiently small compared to the cohesive zone. The interface element is implemented in the finite element code ABAQUS 6.4 using the user subroutine UEL.

Analytical Model

The present cohesive element was applied to simulate the damage propagation in cross-ply laminates $[0_2/90_2]_{2S}$ under static indentation. Dimensions of the numerical model are 30 mm x 40 mm x 2.26 mm. Only a quarter of the model inside the support cut-out was analyzed as shown in Fig. 11. In present analysis, in order to reduce the computational cost,

Fig. 10: Relationship between energy density function and tractions

only the center region of 16 mm x 16 mm was modeled by three-dimensional 20-node solid element (C3D20) and 15-node solid element (C3D15) and other region was modeled by three-dimensional 8-node composite shell element (S8R), where the shell and solid regions were connected by multi-point constraints (MPC) in ABAQUS option. The material properties used for the laminates and the cohesive element are summarized in Table 1 and 2. The value of 10^4 N/mm is used for the penalty stiffness k_c based on previous analyses. The boundary conditions were applied in accordance with the test condition and displacement-loading was applied to center of the laminates.

Two types of analysis models, only delamination model (Model A) and delamination-transverse crack model (Model B), are considered in order to examine the effect of transverse crack on the delamination propagation. In the Model A, cohesive elements are introduced only to simulate the delamination propagation. In the Model B, the cohesive elements are used for the propagations of transverse crack in each layer as

Table 1 Properties of the cross-ply laminates

E_{11}^*	$E_{22}^* = E_{33}$	$\nu_{12}^* = \nu_{13}$	ν_{23}	$G_{12} = G_{13}$	G_{23}
156.3 GPa	8.9 GPa	0.34	0.45	5.6 GPa	3.07 GPa

* Referred to JAXA-ACDB [14]

Table 2 Properties of the cohesive element

G_c	T_{wc}	$T_{uc} = T_{vc}$	Δw_c	$\Delta u_c = \Delta v_c$	Δw_0	$\Delta u_0 = \Delta v_0$
0.4 kJ/m ²	24.3 MPa	48.5 MPa	1.0×10^{-2} mm	5.0×10^{-3} mm	3.0×10^{-2} mm	1.5×10^{-2} mm

Fig.12: Relationship between the reaction force of the indented position and deflection of the cross-ply laminates

to bottom through thickness. In order to stabilize the convergence of solution, a standard Newton-Raphson iterative approach with a control option was used for the nonlinear finite element analysis.

Analytical Results

Figure 12 shows the relationship between the reaction force of the indented position and deflection of the cross-ply laminates. The propagation of delamination occurs at the center of interlaminar plane with some reduction of the stiffness in the Model A, since transverse shear stress across the delamination is usually large at its middle surface. After that, the stiffness reduction becomes clearly when all the delaminations propagate. In the Model B, the bending crack propagated at very low load of 0.25 kN and all the transverse cracks propagated at 0.4 kN simultaneously, where the load decreases suddenly. In present model, mesh refinement through the thickness is not sufficient to simulate the propagation of transverse cracks. Therefore, all the transverse cracks tend to propagate at such low load level.

The predicted delamination shapes obtained by Model A and B are compared in Fig. 13. All the delaminations propagated in the fiber direction of the layer below their interfaces. The damage size of Model B is slightly larger than that of Model A because the delamination tends to propagate along transverse crack tip. Delamination 6, which is adjacent to the bottom layer of Model B is elongated along the bending crack in the layer below and sharp at the tip, although the tendency of delamination propagation is basically similar to the case of only delaminations. The result of Model B can well explain the characteristics of the realistic damage shape.

CONCLUSION

A damage growth problem in cross-ply CFRP laminates under low-velocity impact and static indentation was studied. Both tests gave essentially the same results for damage modes, delamination size and deformations of the laminates. The different stages of the damage growth were observed by experiments and simulated by finite element analysis. Bending and in-plane stresses induce large tensile strains on the backside of the laminate, hence there is many cracks in the backside layers. After the damage initiation, the laminate becomes tensile condition even in the top surface, which causes extensive delamination propagation. A numerical model with a cohesive interface element is applied to the

well as delamination. The fracture toughness of the transverse crack is equal to that of the delamination. As shown in Figure 11, the geometry of the transverse crack is simplified based on the microscopic observation of the cross-section (see Fig. 7), which is inclined at 45° in each layer (except for top and bottom layers) and arranged to be parallel to the fiber direction of the layer. Single bending crack is modeled at its center in the bottom layer and there is no transverse crack in the top layer. The number of the 20-node solid and 8-node shell elements is 12,400 and that of cohesive element is 9,000 in Model A. The location of delamination is indicated by the number which increases from top

(a) Model A (b) Model B
 Fig. 13: Comparison of predicted delamination shapes at 0.7 kN

propagation of the delamination and transverse crack in the laminate due to the static indentation. The delamination, which is adjacent to the bottom layer, is elongated along the bending crack and sharp at the crack tip, although the tendency of delamination propagation is basically similar in both cases. The analytical solutions converge smoothly and the result obtained from the delaminations-transverse cracks model well explains the characteristics of the realistic damage. The effect of transverse cracks on predicted delamination propagation is significant. The present method will be a good tool to simulate the damage growth problem for more practical composite structures.

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